

TECHNICAL REPORT

Deploying a High Availability OpenStack-Ansible Cloud with Ceph for Bioinformatics Applications

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Introduction

Building a private cloud infrastructure is increasingly essential for research institutions, particularly in the field of Bioinformatics, where data-intensive projects require dedicated and secure platforms to support complex analyses and collaborations. In the era of Big Data, AI, and high-performance computing (HPC), researchers need scalable and flexible computing resources that can handle intricate simulations, massive genomic datasets, and high-speed analytics. A private cloud infrastructure offers several key advantages, including enhanced control over data management, security, and compliance, which are critical in handling sensitive genetic and health-related information.

Unlike public clouds, where resources are shared and data authority may be a concern, private clouds give research institutions full governance over their own infrastructure, ensuring that sensitive data remains within the organization's control and complies with institutional policies or legal requirements. Moreover, private cloud environments can be tailored to meet the specific computational needs of Bioinformatics workflows, supporting high availability, storage optimization, and resource allocation aligned with scientific goals.

Additionally, private clouds foster collaboration among multidisciplinary research teams allowing them to securely share resources and computational tools. This kind of infrastructure also supports long-term research sustainability by providing cost-effective resource allocation and enabling the integration of cutting-edge technologies like OpenStack, Ceph, and Ansible for seamless automation and scalability. Ultimately, a well-architected private cloud enables research institutions to accelerate innovation, and stay competitive in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

Goals

The primary purpose of this technical report is to describe the Cloud infrastructure implemented for the automation and management of a private Cloud environment that has been built within the Institute of Biomedical Technologies of the CNR (National Research Council) which aims to provide researchers, as well as those collaborating on shared projects, with useful services in terms of virtual machines and storage for bioinformatics analyses and secure management of data.

Using OpenStack to build a Cloud infrastructure offers several significant advantages, making it a strong choice for organizations and institutions looking to deploy private or hybrid Clouds.

Specifically, the report will highlight the technical choices made regarding the main features of a Cloud environment based on OpenStack-Ansible and integrated with the Ceph storage system, including software, networking, and hardware configuration.

What is OpenStack?

OpenStack is an open-source software [1], so there are no proprietary restrictions in using it. This means that administrators have complete control over infrastructure allowing them to customize and modify it based on their specific needs. The active global community guarantees continuous improvement of the platform, providing regular updates, security patches and new features.

OpenStack uses pools of virtual resources to create and manage private and public Clouds. The tools that constitute the OpenStack platform are called "projects" or "services" because they actually manage the core Cloud computing services, such as compute, networking, storage, image and identity management. Optional projects may also be included to create customized deployable Clouds.

In virtualization, resources like storage, CPU and RAM are abstracted from various proprietary programs and separated by a hypervisor before being distributed as needed. OpenStack uses a consistent set of application programming interfaces (APIs) to add an additional layer of abstraction to these virtual resources, organizing them into distinct pools that support standard Cloud computing tools, which administrators and users interact with directly.

Why OpenStack-Ansible?

OpenStack-Ansible (OSA) [2] helps manage private Cloud infrastructure more efficiently by providing automated deployment, scalability, and flexibility while reducing complexity and operational overhead. In our specific use case, OSA automates the deployment and management of OpenStack services. This reduces the complexity of manually setting up services across

multiple nodes, making deployment faster and more reliable. OSA can scale with the infrastructure. Whether you have a few nodes or hundreds, it can handle scaling up or down by defining the architecture in playbooks. This is ideal for managing a growing private Cloud infrastructure. Furthermore, Ansible's declarative approach lets the administrators customize their OpenStack deployment to meet specific needs, such as different storage backends, network configurations, and security policies. This flexibility allows us to tailor the private Cloud to our specific use cases. By using Ansible, all servers can be deployed consistently, ensuring reliable environments recreation and minimizing human error. A private Cloud using OSA supports multi-tenancy, enabling different teams or users to operate in isolated environments, all within the same infrastructure. It also helps with workload separation and security, an important feature in the bioinformatics domain. It also offers a cost-effective solution by eliminating the need for expensive proprietary cloud management platforms and integrates well with other DevOp tools, monitoring tools (e.g., Prometheus, Zabbix), and CI/CD pipelines, enabling streamlined operations for continuous integration and delivery.

General OpenStack Architecture

OpenStack-Ansible is an open-source deployment tool designed for deploying and managing OpenStack in a flexible, automated way. Its architecture revolves around the concept of using Ansible playbooks [3] to configure and manage the various components of OpenStack across multiple nodes in a Cloud infrastructure. OpenStack server types can be divided into four classes: controller, compute, network and storage nodes. In our infrastructure both controller and network node functionalities are combined on the same server due to the server's capabilities, meaning a single server handles both roles (Figure 1). In the controller node the OpenStack services are deployed in containers, in our specific case LXC containers (as suggested in case of OSA infrastructure), which provide isolation and consistency. Each OpenStack service runs in its own container. This configuration, together with the redundancy of the nodes, implements High

Availability and makes it easy to manage updates, security and scaling without interrupting the entire system.

Figure 1: *A schema of the OpenStack Environment with Ceph Storage*

Ansible, as an orchestration tool, plays a critical role by automating the entire deployment and management process. It uses YAML-based playbooks templates to define tasks, roles, and variables that configure OpenStack services. These playbooks are responsible for installing necessary packages, configuring services, managing networks, and ensuring that the deployed environment is consistent and reliable.

The architecture emphasizes high availability and scalability. Controllers, which manage the core services like identity, messaging and networking, can be configured in a redundant manner to ensure that if one fails, others continue to handle the load. Compute nodes, responsible for running virtual machines or containers, can be scaled horizontally by adding more servers, with Ansible playbooks automatically integrating them into the environment.

Networking in OSA is managed using software-defined networking (SDN) approaches [4], such as Linux bridges, providing flexible virtualized networking across the physical and virtual infrastructure. The architecture also supports integration with external storage solutions, allowing for diverse backend storage options, from Ceph to traditional network-attached storage.

OpenStack-Ansible's modular and container-based design ensures that the environment is adaptable to both small and large-scale deployments, focusing on automation, repeatability, and ease of maintenance.

The **OpenStack services** themselves form the backbone of the cloud platform. These services include:

- **Nova** (compute) for managing virtual machines;
- **Neutron** (networking) for managing networks, subnets, and routing;
- **Cinder** (block storage) and **Swift** (object storage) for handling data storage;
- **Keystone** (identity service) for authentication and authorization;
- **Glance** (image service) for managing VM images;
- **Horizon**, the web-based dashboard, for user and admin interaction with the Cloud.

In addition, **Galera Cluster** for MySQL and **RabbitMQ** for messaging ensure high availability and performance for the database and message queue services. In particular, Galera provides a replicated MySQL database across multiple nodes, while RabbitMQ handles communication between OpenStack services.

The **playbooks and roles** in OSA are predefined sets of instructions that automate the configuration of these components. Playbooks contain the tasks that Ansible executes, while roles organize these tasks into reusable units, making the deployment modular and customizable. OSA comes with a collection of roles to deploy and configure each OpenStack service, allowing operators to easily manage and customize their environment.

The OSA Configuration workflow can be outlined as in the following Figure 2:

Figure 2: A scheme of the OpenStack-Ansible Configuration Workflow

Requirements and recommendations

Software requirements for OpenStack-Ansible

Following official [documentation](#), all hosts within the OSA environment meet minimum requirements. For our specific infrastructure the requirements are the following:

- OS Ubuntu 22.04.5 LTS (Jammy Jellyfish)
- Secure Shell (SSH) client and server that support public key authentication
- Python 3.10.12
- en_US.UTF-8 as the locale

While planning compute and storage resources for an OpenStack environment, several factors have been considered, such as workload types, expected growth, performance requirements, and availability.

Compute recommendations

Computational servers require multicore processors in which Virtualization Technology abstracts hardware abstraction that allows multiple workloads to share a common set of resources. On

shared virtualized hardware, a variety of workloads can co-locate while maintaining full isolation from each other, freely migrate across infrastructures, and scale as needed.ensures. This feature provides significant improvements in terms of performance and increases the security of virtualized environments.

Control servers, on the other hand, require high-performance multicore processors to provide management services. For example, services like MySQL can benefit from the use of more CPU cores.

Below are the specifications of the 110 compute nodes (6 of them equipped with GPUs) available in our infrastructure:

CPU

- **Workload Type:** expecting a CPU-intensive workload (e.g., scientific computing, data analyses), the CPU overcommit ratios (vCPU to physical CPU core) typically range from **1:1** (for high-performance workloads) to **8:1**.
- **Architecture:** CPU processors (2xIntel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6238R per server) count 28 Total Cores 28, 56 Total Threads 56, 4.00 GHz of Max Turbo Frequency, 2.20 GHz of Processor Base Frequency and 38.5 MB of Cache Memory

RAM

- Each compute node is equipped with 1,5 TB of RAM. Memory overcommitment should be kept to a minimum, especially for memory-intensive workloads like databases or caching services.

GPU

- The GPU compute nodes are equipped with NVIDIA A100 40Gb Tensor Core GPUs which deliver high acceleration at every scale. A100 provides up to 20X higher performance over the prior NVIDIA Volta™ generation and efficiently scales up or be partitioned into seven isolated GPU instances with Multi-Instance GPU (MIG), providing a unified platform that enables elastic data centers to dynamically adjust to shifting workload demands.

Storage recommendations

When configuring storage for OpenStack, a solid design strategy is crucial for ensuring scalability, reliability, and performance. The choice of storage backend depends on specific use cases, and OpenStack's flexibility allows for various storage solutions to be integrated seamlessly.

One common approach, which is the one we chose, is leveraging Ceph [5], an open-source, software-defined storage platform, which works well for block, object, and file storage solutions in a distributed and scalable manner. Ceph's replication and erasure coding features provide redundancy, ensuring data durability even in case of hardware failure and its integration with OpenStack services like Nova, Cinder and Glance makes it a popular choice. When selecting a storage backend, performance is a key consideration. For high-performance applications,

deploying SSD-based storage can help achieve low-latency access to data. On the other hand, HDDs offer cost-effective solutions for archival or less I/O-intensive applications, where capacity is more important than speed. For our implementation we used SSD to leverage the metadata and both HDD and SSD disks available on our storage servers as Ceph Object Storage Disks (OSDs)

Networking is also integral to storage performance. Ensuring that your storage network is isolated from your public network will prevent traffic bottlenecks. Additionally, enabling jumbo frames and using high-bandwidth (10 Gbps or higher) networks for storage traffic are essential for minimizing latency and maximizing throughput, especially in large-scale environments where storage replication and recovery can place a heavy load on the network.

Ceph is often preferred due to its deep integration with OpenStack services. It allows services like Nova to boot instances directly from Ceph-backed volumes and facilitates snapshot management for Cinder. Glance can store images directly in Ceph's RADOS object store, providing a single storage backend for multiple services, which simplifies management. CephFS, its file storage component, is also useful when integrated with Manila to provide shared file systems for users or applications that require POSIX-compliant storage.

Maintaining a balance between performance, redundancy, and cost is critical when designing the storage architecture for OpenStack-Ansible. You must also consider the scalability of your storage system. Ceph, for instance, is ideal because it scales horizontally by simply adding more OSD nodes. This capability is crucial as your cloud infrastructure grows. Additionally, automating the deployment and configuration of storage components through Ansible roles simplifies management and ensures consistency across your environment.

Ultimately, the right storage strategy will depend on your performance needs, budget, and the expected growth of your cloud environment. Whether using Ceph, traditional storage systems, or a hybrid approach, aligning storage choices with workload requirements and future scalability is key to building a robust OpenStack-Ansible environment.

Different hosts have different requirements depending on the services that need to be run:

- Deployment host (OSA host): at least 10GB of disk is needed to maintain repositories and additional software.
- Compute host: disk space is dependent on the number of instances that are running on the different nodes and the disk of each instance. Disks must prioritize high I/O throughput with low latency.
- Storage host: these are the servers that consume the most disk.
- Infrastructure (control plane) host: contains services that use storage intensively, such as glance and MariaDB. A minimum of 100GB of disk is required.
- Logging host: the installation via Ansible generates a significant amount of logs. Logs come from a variety of sources, including services running in containers, the containers themselves, and the physical . A minimum of 50GB of disk space is required.

Our infrastructure counts 110 storage nodes available. Their specifications are listed in Tab. 5 below.

Networking recommendations

In an OpenStack environment, network design plays a critical role in the overall performance, scalability, and reliability of the Cloud infrastructure. A well-architected network ensures that workloads and services are efficiently distributed, and critical communication between OpenStack components remains uninterrupted.

It is essential to segregate network traffic into different planes to avoid congestion and improve security, separating networks for management, storage, and public-facing traffic. The **management network** handles internal communication between OpenStack services like API requests, database operations, and message queues. This network is crucial for the control plane of the cloud, so it should be low-latency and highly reliable. The **storage network** is used for traffic between compute nodes and storage backends like Ceph, and should have high throughput and minimal latency, as storage operations can be bandwidth-intensive. Lastly, the **public or external network** is where tenant VMs access the internet or external services, and its performance will depend on the workloads hosted in the cloud.

High bandwidth and low-latency connections are important across all these networks, but particularly for the storage and public-facing traffic. A 10 Gbps network is generally recommended for OpenStack deployments, especially for large-scale environments, and leveraging higher speeds (25 Gbps or 40 Gbps) may be necessary as your infrastructure scales.

For highly available and fault-tolerant networking, redundancy at both the physical and virtual layers is critical. Deploying **bonded interfaces** or **LACP (Link Aggregation Control Protocol)** provides failover and load balancing across multiple network interfaces, ensuring that traffic continues flowing even if a physical link fails.

For the best performance, availability, and scalability, it would be advisable to have the following features:

- **Bonded network interfaces**, which increase performance, reliability, or both (depending on the bonding architecture)
- **VLAN offloading**, which improves performance by handling the addition and removal of VLAN tags in hardware, rather than in the server's main CPU
- **Gigabit or 10 Gigabit Ethernet**, which supports higher network speeds and can also improve storage performance when using the Block Storage service

Implementation

Networking

The network architecture implemented in our infrastructure is an IP Fabric LEAF-SPINE based on open standard protocols that behaves externally as a single automated Virtual Fabric logical system.

In order to eliminate "single points of failure" the infrastructure includes redundancy for all hardware components, including switches, uplinks among LEAF, SPINE, LAG, etc.

Our networking infrastructure (see Figure 3) meets the following minimum technical requirements:

- Implementation of a Layer 3 IP Fabric LEAF-SPINE (control plane);
- Routed interconnection between Spine and Leaf is Point-to-Point L3 (no port-channel);
- Each pair of LEAFs interconnected in MLAG, operating logically as a single device;
- Connection between SPINE and COMPUTE LEAF via AOC QSFP 100GbE cables. At least 1 uplink per LEAF to a single SPINE;
- Connection between the COMPUTE LEAF and SERVERS, equipped with 2 SFP28 ports, via AOC SFP28 25GbE cables;
- Connection between the STORAGE LEAF and Parallel Storage System via AOC QSFP 40GbE cables;
- Uplink connection between SERVICE MANAGEMENT SWITCH and COMPUTE/STORAGE LEAF via 10GbE cables;
- Network infrastructure with Active/Active Virtual Gateway, to reduce IP address usage;
- Use of the iBGP routing protocol for peering between LEAF pairs in MLAG (Multi-chassis Link Aggregation Group).

Switch Configuration

MLAG is a technology that improves the availability and efficiency of data center topologies by eliminating the problem of oversubscription and fully utilizing the available bandwidth.

Main Advantages:

- Aggregation of multiple ports on two switches, creating a single logical entity.
- Increased bandwidth without blocking imposed by the Spanning Tree Protocol (STP).
- Optimal use of bandwidth: all active paths can carry traffic.

- Compatibility with static LAGs and LACP, without the need for proprietary protocols.
- Active-active Layer 2 redundancy.

MLAG connects two cooperating switches (MLAG peer switches) via a "peer link". This link exchanges control information and carries traffic for devices connected to only one peer without alternative paths. In a traditional topology, STP blocks 50% of the links; with MLAG, STP sees the MLAG domain as a single switch, so no links are blocked.

Interoperability with Other Features:

1. VLANs: VLAN parameters (e.g., access VLAN, trunk mode) are configured identically on both peers to avoid traffic loss.
2. LACP (Link Aggregation Control Protocol): Should be applied to all MLAG interfaces, including the peer link, to synchronize control packets.
3. Static MACs: Static MAC addresses configured on an MLAG interface are automatically replicated to the peer.

MLAG ensures high availability, bandwidth efficiency, and active redundancy without disrupting compatibility with standard protocols like LACP.

Link Aggregation ensures increased reliability and availability, so that, in case of a physical link failure, traffic is automatically reassigned to other links in the group, a better use of physical resources (traffic can be balanced across physical links) and a bandwidth increment compared to single link.

Figure 3: *A scheme of the IP Fabric LEAF-SPINE implementation*

The data center is connected to the GARR network through high-speed 10 Gbps connections, established with the LEAF01 and LEAF02 switches using the BGP (Border Gateway Protocol) on VLANs 4091 and 4092. The flow of network packets follows a precise path: once received, the packets are routed to the firewalls (a cluster of 2 Forcepoint NGFW), which perform filtering and security operations. Subsequently, the packets are redirected by the firewalls back to the LEAF01 and LEAF02 devices, to then be forwarded to their final destination as see in Figure 4.

Figure 4: *A scheme of the network incoming packets*

Network Architecture

OpenStack-Ansible supports a number of different network architectures, and can be deployed using multiple network interfaces or bonded interfaces for production workloads; the OpenStack-Ansible reference architecture segments traffic using VLANs across multiple network interfaces or bonds.

Due to our hardware infrastructure, we bond two interfaces connected to two different leaf switches to prevent network failover.

The networks used in our OSA configuration are summarised in the following Tab.1:

Network Type	CIDR Network	VLAN
Management	10.10.0.0/22	10
Tunnel (GENEVE)	10.10.40.0/22	30 (401-1000)
Storage	10.10.20.0/22	20
Tunnel (VLAN)		2023-2040

Tab.1: *OSA network*

In OpenStack, traffic segmentation is a crucial part of the architecture. It ensures that different types of network traffic (e.g. management, storage, tunnel, etc) are isolated from each other. This isolation is typically achieved using **VLANs** (Virtual Local Area Networks), each assigned to a

specific type of traffic. As it can be seen from Tab.1, each VLAN represents a distinct type of traffic.

The **Management Network**, provides management and communication between the infrastructure and OpenStack services running in containers. It uses a dedicated VLAN connected to the **br-mgmt** bridge, and it is also used as the primary interface to interact with the server. This interface should be defined in every server and is used by OSA to configure and manage the system.

The **Tunnel (GENEVE) Network** provides connectivity between hosts for the purpose of tunnelling encapsulated traffic using GENEVE protocols. It uses a dedicated VLAN (ID 30) connected to the br-vxlan bridge. Geneve is designed to recognize and accommodate changing capabilities and needs of different devices in network virtualization. It provides a framework for tunneling rather than being prescriptive about the entire system. Geneve defines the content of the metadata flexibly that is added during encapsulation and tries to adapt to various virtualization scenarios allowing software defined networks.

The **Storage Network** provides segregated access to Block Storage from OpenStack services such as Cinder and Glance. The **storage network** uses a dedicated VLAN (ID 20) typically connected to the **br-storage** bridge; this includes traffic to backend storage system such as Ceph, NFS or iSCSI that OpenStack services rely on to store data.

The **Tunnel (VLAN) Network** provides access to specific VLAN defined at switch and Firewall level, the more important VLAN is the provider network (ID 2023) that is the external/public network.

Due to our infrastructure we use bridges in this configuration (br-mgmt, br-storage, br-vxlan, and br-vlan) to enable the bonding of multiple network interfaces and VLANs, allowing virtual machines or services within OpenStack to interact with each other on different types of networks. Each bridge is mapped to a specific VLAN, making sure that traffic remains isolated and flows correctly within the respective network.

This type of configuration must be configured in the OSA yaml configuration file as shown in the Tab.2 below.

<pre>management_bridge: "br-mgmt" provider_networks: - network: container_bridge: "br-mgmt" container_type: "veth" container_interface: "eth1" ip_from_q: "management" type: "raw" group_binds: - all_containers - hosts is_management_address: true</pre>	<pre>- network: container_bridge: "br-vlan" container_type: "veth" container_interface: "eth11" network_interface: "bond0" type: "vlan" range: "2023:2040" net_name: "vlan" group_binds: - neutron_ovn_controller</pre>
--	---

<pre> is_container_address: false - network: container_bridge: "br-vxlan" container_type: "veth" container_interface: "eth10" network_interface: "bond0.30" ip_from_q: "tunnel" type: "geneve" range: "401:1000" net_name: "vxlan" group_binds: - neutron_ovn_controller </pre>	<pre> - network: container_bridge: "br-storage" container_type: "veth" container_interface: "eth2" network_interface: "bond0.20" ip_from_q: "storage" type: "raw" group_binds: - glance_api - cinder_api - cinder_volume - manila_share - nova_compute - ceph-mon - ceph-mds - ceph-osd </pre>
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Tab.2: *OSA network configuration*

This segmented approach aligns with OpenStack-Ansible's best practices for deploying an enterprise-grade, production-ready OpenStack cloud. Each node (compute, storage, controller) communicates with other nodes on these predefined networks, while tenant workloads have their traffic isolated through VXLANs.

Ansible Deployment Host

Following OSA recommendations for a production environment, a separate deployment host has been prepared for containing Ansible configuration and orchestrating the OpenStack-Ansible installation on the other target hosts. For the CNR-ITB Cloud infrastructure, Ubuntu 22.04.5 LTS (Jammy Jellyfish) x86_64 has been installed on a Virtual Machine based on the VMware virtual platform, with 4 Intel Xeon Gold CPU cores and 8 GB of RAM.

The main elements of the deployment host are: playbook directory, roles directory and configuration directory. The playbook is the first relevant directory that is installed and is responsible for downloading all OpenStack roles that contribute to the installation of OpenStack services and the initialization of the configuration directory. In this directory there are scripts that manage the inventory list, the services password and the playbooks for the OpenStack installation.

The installation procedure can be divided in three steps: hosts configuration, infrastructure configuration and OpenStack configuration. In OpenStack-Ansible each step is represented by a specific playbook that, based on the configuration file, executes the specified service playbook.

The configuration directory is the main point of configuration for OpenStack-Ansible. In this directory are defined specific host variables in the custom directory (*host_vars* and *group_vars*) and two important configuration files: *openstack_user_config.yml* and *user_variables.yml*. In Tab.3 there is an example for the specific host configuration that depends on the disk id of each server.

<pre> lvm_volumes: - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae8432a91 db: /dev/vg-sds/CEPHMETA-1 - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae8433679 db: /dev/vg-sds/CEPHMETA-10 - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae8523051 db: /dev/vg-sds/CEPHMETA-2 - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae8433b25 db: /dev/vg-sds/CEPHMETA-3 - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae8524bf1 db: /dev/vg-sds/CEPHMETA-4 - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae84ad6ad db: /dev/vg-sds/CEPHMETA-5 - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae84ae2fd db: /dev/vg-sds/CEPHMETA-6 - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae84ad3a1 db: /dev/vg-sds/CEPHMETA-7 - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae8433a25 db: /dev/vg-sds/CEPHMETA-8 - data: /dev/vg-sds/CEPHOSD-sds db: /dev/vg-sds/CEPHMETA-9 </pre>	<pre> - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae8433dbd db: /dev/vg-sdt/CEPHMETA-11 - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae8432ccd db: /dev/vg-sdt/CEPHMETA-12 - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae8433e25 db: /dev/vg-sdt/CEPHMETA-13 - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae843377d db: /dev/vg-sdt/CEPHMETA-14 - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae8432b15 db: /dev/vg-sdt/CEPHMETA-15 - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae8432c61 db: /dev/vg-sdt/CEPHMETA-16 - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae84337e5 db: /dev/vg-sdt/CEPHMETA-17 - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae8433fd1 db: /dev/vg-sdt/CEPHMETA-18 - data: /dev/disk/by-id/wwn-0x5000039ae84adcd5 db: /dev/vg-sdt/CEPHMETA-19 - data: /dev/vg-sdt/CEPHOSD-sdt db: /dev/vg-sdt/CEPHMETA-20 </pre>
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Tab.3: *Example of a custom host yaml file*

Configuration File: *openstack_user_config.yml*

The *openstack_user_config.yml* file is the core of the infrastructure configuration; it is responsible for the server classification (infrastructure, compute and storage), network configuration and services installation.

While the network configuration was shown in Tab.2, Tab.4 contains a snippet for the classification of the hosts, which is necessary to OSA for the installation and basic configuration of the specific services.

<pre> _infrastructure_hosts: &infrastructure_hosts infra12: ip: 10.10.2.12 infra21: ip: 10.10.2.21 </pre>	<pre> ceph-osd_hosts: osdbm71: ip: 10.10.2.71 osdbm72: ip: 10.10.2.72 </pre>
---	--

<pre> infra31: ip: 10.10.2.31 compute_hosts: &compute_hosts computebm38: ip: 10.10.2.38 computebm40: ip: 10.10.2.40 computebm41: ip: 10.10.2.41 [...]</pre>	<pre> osdbm73: ip: 10.10.2.73 [...] haproxy_hosts: haproxy1: ip: 10.10.2.5 host_vars: ext_ip: 193.205.32.5 haproxy2: ip: 10.10.2.6 host_vars: ext_ip: 193.205.32.6</pre>
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Tab.4. *OSA Host Classification*

Based on their characteristics, the servers have been classified and configured as shown in the Tab.5.

Type	#	CPU	Memory	OS	Note
Controller Node	3	2X Intel Xeon Gold 6238R (56 cores) @ 2.200GHz	1.5 TB	Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS x86_64	4 x HDD 2.2TB 2 x SSD 1.5TB
Compute Node	26	2X Intel Xeon Gold 6238R (56 cores) @ 2.200GHz	1.5 TB	Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS x86_64	1x NVIDIA GA100 [A100 PCIe 40GB] 4 x HDD 2.2TB 2 x SSD 1.5TB
Storage Node	28	2X Intel Xeon Gold 6238R (56 cores) @ 2.200GHz	256 GB	Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS x86_64	18 x HDD 2.2TB 2 x SSD 3.5TB
Load Balancer Node	2	2X Intel Xeon Gold 6238R (56 cores) @ 2.200GHz	1.5 TB	Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS x86_64	4 x HDD 2.2TB 2 x SSD 1.5TB

Tab.5: *Host Features and Classification*

The last part of the *openstack_user_config.yml* file is dedicated to the selection and installation of the services needed by OpenStack for the defined Cloud infrastructure. Tab.6 contains a snippet for the selection of services with the specific host where to install the service.

<pre> # keystone identity_hosts: *infrastructure_hosts</pre>	<pre> # nova api, conductor, etc services compute_infra_hosts: *infrastructure_hosts</pre>
--	--

<pre># cinder api services storage-infra_hosts: *infrastructure_hosts # cinder volume hosts (Ceph RBD-backed) storage_hosts: *infrastructure_hosts # glance image_hosts: *infrastructure_hosts # placement placement-infra_hosts: *infrastructure_hosts</pre>	<pre># heat orchestration_hosts: *infrastructure_hosts # horizon dashboard_hosts: *infrastructure_hosts # neutron server, agents (L3, etc), OVN controller network_hosts: *infrastructure_hosts network-gateway_hosts: *compute_hosts network-northd_hosts: *infrastructure_hosts</pre>
--	---

Tab.6: *OSA Service installation*

Configuration File: *user_variables.yml*

OpenStack-Ansible installs and configures the defined services in the *openstack_user_config.yml* with the default parameters; the *user_variables.yml* file is the core for the customization of the services by overriding the default settings through the use of a simple set of configuration entries.

Tab.7 shows the override configuration for the two HAproxy nodes, the load balancer IP for communication is handled by the keepalived daemon and this code snippet configures the virtual IP on a specific interface for management and external network and also provides the SSL certificates for the secure communication.

<pre>haproxy_keepalived_external_vip_cidr: "193.205.32.254/32" haproxy_keepalived_internal_vip_cidr: "10.10.2.254/32" haproxy_keepalived_external_interface: br-vlan haproxy_keepalived_internal_interface: br-mgmt haproxy_user_ssl_cert: /etc/OpenStack_deploy/ssl.d/cloud.cnrbiomics.it/fullchain1.pem haproxy_user_ssl_key: /etc/OpenStack_deploy/ssl.d/cloud.cnrbiomics.it/privkey1.pem haproxy_user_ssl_ca_cert: /etc/OpenStack_deploy/ssl.d/cloud.cnrbiomics.it/isrgrootx1.pem</pre>

Tab.7: *OSA HAproxy service override*

As highlighted in several parts, the network configuration is relevant for the performance and functionality of OpenStack. In Tab.8 a snippet of code is shown for the Neutron override where the used plugins and the type of accepted networks are reported.

<pre>neutron_l2_population: True neutron_plugin_type: ml2.ovn neutron_plugin_base:</pre>
--

```

- router
- metering
- firewall_v2
- vpnaas
- ovn-router
- neutron.services.ovn_l3.plugin.OVNL3RouterPlugin
- qos

neutron_ml2_drivers_type: "vlan,local,geneve,flat"

```

Tab.8: *OSA Neutron service override*

Keystone is an OpenStack service that provides API client authentication, service discovery and distributed multi-tenant authorization by implementing OpenStack's Identity API. The default behaviour is to use the Galera database to store and manage information. With the snippet of code shown in Tab.9, we have added a specific domain of authentication through a LDAP server that manages all the infrastructure users and authorizes only the users belonging to a specific group.

```

keystone_ldap:
  CNRBiomics:
    url: "ldap://freeipa-ba.cnrbiomics.it,ldap://freeipa-mi.cnrbiomics.it"
    user: uid=cloud,cn=sysaccounts,cn=etc,dc=cnrbiomics,dc=it
    password: *****
    suffix: "dc=cnrbiomics,dc=it"
    user_tree_dn: "cn=users,cn=accounts,dc=cnrbiomics,dc=it"
    user_objectclass: "inetOrgPerson"
    user_id_attribute: "cn"
    user_name_attribute: "uid"
    user_mail_attribute: mail
    group_tree_dn: "cn=groups,cn=accounts,dc=cnrbiomics,dc=it"
    group_objectclass: groupOfNames
    group_id_attribute: cn
    group_name_attribute: cn
    group_member_attribute: member
    group_desc_attribute: description
    user_filter: (memberOf=cn=cloud,cn=groups,cn=accounts,dc=cnrbiomics,dc=it)
    group_filter: (cn=cloud*)

```

Tab.9: *OSA Keystone service override*

Finally Tab.10 shows the configuration to enable the multidomain support in the OpenStack dashboard and the customization of the logo.

```

horizon_keystone_multidomain_support: True
horizon_keystone_multidomain_dropdown: True

```

```
horizon_keystone_multidomain_choices: "'(CNRBiomics', 'CNRBiomics'), ('Default', 'Default')'"
horizon_session_timeout: 14400
horizon_custom_uploads:
  logo:
    src: "/etc/OpenStack_deploy/horizon/CNRBiOmics_ITB_ELIXIR_logo_splash.svg"
    dest: "img/logo.svg"
  logo_splash:
    src: "/etc/OpenStack_deploy/horizon/CNRBiOmics_ITB_ELIXIR_logo_splash.svg"
    dest: "img/logo-splash.svg"
```

Tab.10: *OSA Horizon service override*

Controller Nodes

Within an OpenStack-Ansible infrastructure, the controller nodes are responsible for managing the core services of the Cloud. They handle the orchestration, scheduling, and API endpoints required for the operation of various OpenStack components. Controllers manage services such as identity (Keystone), image management (Glance), network orchestration (Neutron), and compute scheduling (Nova). These nodes also ensure database and message queue functionality, facilitating communication and coordination between services. In our setup controller nodes are configured for high availability, meaning that multiple controllers work together to ensure redundancy, load balancing, and failover.

Following best practice and considering that services running on the controller nodes are crucial for the Cloud infrastructure functioning, we chose a replica 3 configuration. By using three controllers, we ensured that the core OpenStack's services remain operational even if one or more nodes fail. This is achieved by distributing the services across 3 nodes and using clustering mechanisms or load balancers to manage requests. If one controller node goes down, the remaining two can continue handling the load, minimizing downtime.

Compute Nodes with GPU Configuration

A compute node in OpenStack is basically a server in the OpenStack Cloud computing platform. It is essentially a host where the virtual machines or instances run. The core component of the OpenStack Compute is Nova that provides these resources, handling the lifecycle of compute instances in an OpenStack environment.

In our environment the most relevant peculiarity of the compute configuration is the presence of the GPU device. In order to create a GPU-enabled virtual instance, we need to configure the compute node to support GPU passthrough.

We firstly set up the GPU compute node modifying the GRUB in order to enable IOMMU and specifying the GPU device ID for passthrough and specific kernel modules must also be loaded. In order to ensure the system ignores specific MSRs, KVM configuration must be modified setting

the corresponding boolean to TRUE (**options kvm ignore_msrs=1**). Blacklisting default NVIDIA drivers is also necessary.

The **vfiopci** module (a kernel module that allows PCI devices to be passed through directly to VMs or containers) must be added and loaded at startup. This module is commonly used in setups involving GPU passthrough, where the goal is to give a VM or container direct control over a physical device, bypassing the host system's use of the hardware.

In order to whitelist the GPU, Nova configuration must be modified and this can be done through the override configuration in the *user_variables.yml* file. In particular it is important to add **passthrough_whitelist** and edit the **filter_scheduler** for the node selection. The Tab.11 reports the related code snippet.

```
nova_nova_conf_overrides:
  pci:
    passthrough_whitelist: { "vendor_id": "10de", "product_id": "20f1" }
    alias: { "vendor_id":"10de", "product_id":"20f1",
"device_type":"type-PF", "name":"GA100" }
  filter_scheduler:
    max_io_ops_per_host = 10
    enabled_filters = PciPassthroughFilter,ComputeFilter,
    AggregateNumInstancesFilter, AggregateIoOpsFilter,
    ComputeCapabilitiesFilter, ImagePropertiesFilter,
    ServerGroupAntiAffinityFilter,
    ServerGroupAffinityFilter, NUMATopologyFilter
    available_filters = nova.scheduler.filters.all_filters
    host_subset_size = 3
    track_instance_changes = True
```

Tab.11: *OSA Nova service override*

To ensure GPU instances running only on the correct hosts an aggregate (**gpu_hosts**) has been created in Nova availability zone and then the GPU node has been added setting the corresponding property (**gpu=true**) to the aggregate.

To make the new resource available for the users we create a specific flavour (**gpu_flavor**) with custom properties set on it like `aggregate_instance_extra_specs:gpu` set to true and `pci_passthrough:alias` set to `GA100:1` as shown in the code below:

```
OpenStack flavor set gpu_flavor --property "aggregate_instance_extra_specs:gpu=true"
OpenStack flavor set gpu_flavor --property "pci_passthrough:alias"="GA100:1"
```

By following these steps, we have successfully configured an OpenStack environment to support GPU passthrough. This setup ensures virtual machines can fully exploit GPU resources for high-performance computing tasks.

Storage Nodes with Ceph Backend

A storage node in OpenStack is basically a server in the OpenStack cloud computing platform. It is essentially a host that provides storage, volumes and backup for the OpenStack services. In our environment we use Ceph for the storage Backend.

CEPH's architecture revolves around the following key components:

- **OSDs (Object Storage Daemons):** These are the actual storage nodes that store data across the cluster.
- **MONs (Monitors):** Maintain cluster state and ensure consistency by keeping track of OSD status.
- **MDS (Metadata Server):** Used for file-based storage to track metadata when using CephFS (CEPH File System).
- **CRUSH Map:** Determines how data is distributed across OSDs for redundancy and performance optimization. It ensures that data is distributed evenly across the cluster.

Our OpenStack infrastructure can count on several services that can be integrated with CEPH to provide a seamless storage backend:

- **Cinder (Block Storage Service):** CEPH can be used as a backend for block storage. In this case, CEPH RBD (RADOS Block Device) is used to provide virtual block devices. These can be attached to instances as persistent storage.
- **Glance (Image Service):** CEPH can store virtual machine (VM) images in its object storage layer, providing fast and scalable storage for images.
- **Nova (Compute Service):** CEPH can provide backend storage for ephemeral disks using RBD, ensuring that VM instances get high-performance, distributed storage.
- **Swift (Object Storage):** While OpenStack Swift is its own object storage service, CEPH's RADOS Gateway (RGW) can be used to provide object storage services (an S3/Swift API-compatible layer) if you prefer to consolidate all storage under CEPH.

The advantages to use Ceph to serve all the services are:

- **Scalability:** CEPH allows for horizontal scaling. This means you can add more OSD nodes to increase capacity and performance without downtime.
- **Fault Tolerance:** Data is automatically replicated across multiple OSDs, ensuring redundancy and high availability.
- **Unified Storage:** CEPH provides object, block, and file storage under a single platform, reducing the complexity of managing multiple storage systems.
- **High Performance:** CEPH's architecture is designed for parallel access to storage, which improves performance, especially in high-demand environments.

Deploying CEPH with OpenStack-Ansible

CEPH integration can be managed using OpenStack-Ansible, the general outline of how deployment works:

- **Prepare CEPH cluster:** You first need to set up your CEPH cluster by configuring OSDs, MONs, and a CRUSH map.
- **Configure OpenStack services:** You then configure services like Cinder, Glance, Nova, and Manila to use CEPH as their backend.
- **Connect OpenStack to CEPH:** The OpenStack components communicate with CEPH over RADOS, either directly or through an API (like RADOS Gateway).

To integrate CEPH with OpenStack, various configuration files need to be adjusted:

- **Cinder configuration:** You configure the `/etc/cinder/cinder.conf` file to use `rbd` as the backend storage driver.
- **Glance configuration:** The `/etc/glance/glance-api.conf` is updated to use CEPH as the image storage backend.
- **Nova configuration:** The `/etc/nova/nova.conf` is updated to use `rbd` for ephemeral storage.
- **Manila configuration:** The `/etc/manila/manila.conf` is modified to use CEPHFS for shared file systems.

In order to override the default configuration of Ceph, we added the information in the `user_variables.yml` as shown in the Tab.12, this snippet of code allows the configuration of the various pools and in particular the creation of the SSD pool.

```
OpenStack_cinder_pool:
  name: "volumes"
  application: "rbd"
  rule_name: "HDD"

OpenStack_cinder_pool_ssd:
  name: "volumes-ssd"
  application: "rbd"
  rule_name: "SSD"

OpenStack_pools:
- "{{ OpenStack_glance_pool }}"
- "{{ OpenStack_cinder_pool }}"
- "{{ OpenStack_cinder_pool_ssd }}"
- "{{ OpenStack_nova_pool }}"
- "{{ OpenStack_cinder_backup_pool }}"
- "{{ OpenStack_gnocchi_pool }}"
- "{{ OpenStack_cephfs_data_pool }}"
- "{{ OpenStack_cephfs_metadata_pool }}"
```

Tab.12: *OSA Ceph pool configuration*

The snippet of code shown in the Tab.13 implements the configuration of different volume backend RBD and SSD. The RBD volume is the HDD default volume while the SSD is the SSD volume for the workload that requires better W/R performance.

```
cinder_backends:
  RBD:
    volume_driver: cinder.volume.drivers.rbd.RBDDriver
    rbd_pool: volumes
    rbd_ceph_conf: /etc/ceph/ceph.conf
    rbd_store_chunk_size: 8
    volume_backend_name: rbd driver
    rbd_user: "{{ cinder_ceph_client }}"
    rbd_secret_uuid: "{{ cinder_ceph_client_uuid }}"
    report_discard_supported: true
  SSD:
    volume_driver: cinder.volume.drivers.rbd.RBDDriver
    rbd_pool: volumes-ssd
    rbd_ceph_conf: /etc/ceph/ceph.conf
    rbd_store_chunk_size: 8
    volume_backend_name: rbdssd
    rbd_user: "{{ cinder_ceph_client }}"
    rbd_secret_uuid: "{{ cinder_ceph_client_uuid }}"
    report_discard_supported: true
```

Tab.13: *OSA Ceph backends configuration*

Ceph Data and Metadata Management

Ceph uses a CRUSH (Controlled Replication Under Scalable Hashing) algorithm to distribute data across OSDs in the cluster. The CRUSH algorithm allows Ceph clients to calculate where to store or retrieve data objects, resulting in direct interaction with OSDs. This leads to scalability, as clients don't need to communicate with a centralized metadata server to find the location of data.

Within Ceph virtual block devices are provided by RBD (RADOS Block Device) which is a block storage feature of Ceph that allows applications to interact with it as if it were a block device, similar to a physical hard drive. RBDs can be used to store virtual machine disk images, databases, or any application that requires raw block-level storage. It ensures scalability, snapshot provisioning, block device cloning from snapshots and data striping across multiple OSDs.

In OpenStack, Ceph RBD can be used as the backend for the Cinder (block storage) and Glance (image storage) services, allowing virtual machine images and volumes to be stored directly on the Ceph cluster. It enhances performance, scalability, and data redundancy.

In our configuration, the CNR-ITB Cloud storage infrastructure is currently composed of 28 servers (256 GB of RAM per server), each one counting 18 Hard Disk Drives (HDDs, 2.2 TB per disk) and 2 Solid State Disks (SSDs, 3,5 TB per disk). Each disk corresponds to a Ceph OSD, counting 560 OSDs overall.

Logical partitions named as pools are used by Ceph to store objects. Ceph pools ensure resilience so that it is possible to set the number of OSDs that are allowed to fail without any data being lost. In our specific case, using replicated pools the number of OSDs that can fail without data loss is equal to the number of replicas (size = 3).

Furthermore, Ceph configuration uses **Placement Groups** (PGs). PGs are subsets of each logical Ceph pool. They perform the function of placing objects (as a group) into OSDs. Ceph manages data internally at placement-group granularity: this scales better than would managing individual RADOS objects. The larger the number of placement groups the better is the cluster's balancing. The PGs' autoscaler automatically sets the number of placement groups for each pool in order to provide a good balancing without consuming excessive computing resources.

In the storage servers, the two 3.5 TB SSD physical volumes have been partitioned into 10 partitions of 100 MB each to store HDDs' metadata + 1 OSD/SSD of 2.2 TB. As best practice, additional free space of ~3.4 GB (~11%) has been reserved on each SSD for wear leveling purposes.

In order to manage storage resources, LVM (Logical Volume Manager) is used by Ceph to manage storage resources as logical volumes rather than raw disks. For each physical disk, Ceph creates on top via LVM:

- **a logical volume (ceph--af80bd48...-osd--block...)**, which represents a logical unit of allocated storage to manage and abstract the underlying storage of the corresponding OSD;
- **an encrypted block device**, which is managed through Linux device-mapper encryption. The data stored in this Ceph OSD is encrypted for security, meaning any data written to this OSD will be encrypted before being stored on the disk. The LVM logical volume is wrapped in an encrypted layer (**crypt**), ensuring that even if someone accesses the raw disk, the data is unreadable without the encryption key.

Ceph Challenges and Considerations

Tools like **Ceph Dashboard**, **Ceph CLI** and integration with OpenStack's **Horizon dashboard** can help monitor and manage your CEPH cluster, including tracking performance, usage, and health.

The major challenges in the Ceph configuration and utilization are:

- **Network Performance:** Since CEPH uses the network to distribute data across nodes, ensuring a high-performance network (preferably 10 Gbps or higher) is critical.
- **Operational Complexity:** Managing a large CEPH cluster can be complex, and administrators need to monitor cluster health, OSD usage, and replication.
- **Tuning:** CEPH's performance can vary based on the hardware and workload, so tuning parameters like replication factor and CRUSH map is very important.

Testing OpenStack-Ansible Installation and Operativity

OpenStack authentication service is provided by Keystone that implements [OpenStack's Identity API](#). The login web page of CNR-ITB private Cloud infrastructure is the following: <https://cloud-ba.cnrbiomics.it/> (see Figure 5)

Figure 5: *OpenStack Keystone Authentication*

Once logged in, you are redirected to Horizon's Dashboard (see Figure 6):

Figure 6: *OpenStack Horizon Dashboard*

OpenStack's Horizon provides a user-friendly interface for managing the various aspects of an OpenStack Cloud environment. As shown in Figure 6, at the top of the page a navigation bar is provided including information about the active projects (a.k.a. tenants, "Default" in this example) and the user logged in. This bar allows switching between projects or user settings and provides the option to log out or manage API access. It provides a clear and visual summary of Cloud resources, making it easier to monitor usage, limits, and perform administrative tasks like creating and managing instances, storage, and networks.

A sidebar menu that organizes different functionalities into categories can be seen on the left. The **Compute** section is currently active, which contains options like "Overview," "Instances," "Images," "Key Pairs," and "Server Groups." The compute section is primarily focused on managing virtual machines (VMs) and their associated resources. The "Overview" tab, which is open in the image, gives a summary of the Cloud's usage limits across various resources such as instances, vCPUs, RAM, volumes, networks, and security groups.

The main section of the dashboard is currently showing the **Overview**. This space is divided into several pie charts representing the usage limits for different resources. For example, we can see how many **instances** are being used out of the total available, the number of vCPUs and RAM being consumed, and how much **volume storage** is occupied. Additionally, the **Network** section shows the usage of floating IPs, security groups, networks, ports, and routers.

At the bottom, there's a **Usage Summary** section, which allows users to query the usage for a specific time period. This feature provides a detailed look at resource consumption, helping users track how resources such as RAM and vCPUs are being utilized over time.

The following test have been performed following OpenStack User's Guide (<https://docs.OpenStack.org/mitaka/user-guide/>), see Figure 7:

1. Create Flavor
2. Create Image
3. Create Network
4. Create Instance

```
root@infra12-utility-container-892ee8b1:~# openstack server create --flavor Test_Flavor --image
orgia_key --hint host=computebm28 --user-data cloud-init.yaml vm_test_mig_2
+-----+-----+
| Field | Value |
+-----+-----+
| OS-DCF:diskConfig | MANUAL |
| OS-EXT-AZ:availability_zone | |
| OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:host | None |
| OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:hypervisor_hostname | None |
| OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:instance_name | |
| OS-EXT-STS:power_state | NOSTATE |
| OS-EXT-STS:task_state | scheduling |
| OS-EXT-STS:vm_state | building |
| OS-SRV-USG:launched_at | None |
| OS-SRV-USG:terminated_at | None |
| accessIPv4 | |
| accessIPv6 | |
| addresses | |
| adminPass | C3G86ASw5gL9 |
| config_drive | |
| created | 2025-01-23T18:14:09Z |
| flavor | Test_Flavor (91325b40-762b-482e-9bec-b96c0fa73ab4) |
| hostId | |
| id | d66de7b3-640a-49cf-b229-99732a1abb50 |
| image | Ubuntu2205 (dc28c30d-8656-4d9b-9e20-dd37b8380fbf) |
| key_name | giorgia_key |
| name | vm_test_mig_2 |
| progress | 0 |
| project_id | d52aa5313dc24735a9546ff0723f9305 |
| properties | |
| security_groups | name='098cbd7c-0dd2-4994-bf8e-9d8f79397a9f' |
| status | BUILD |
| updated | 2025-01-23T18:14:09Z |
| user_id | a161aee64da541cab4f06b94d49a2064 |
| volumes_attached | |
+-----+-----+
root@infra12-utility-container-892ee8b1:~#
```

Figure 7: *OpenStack server creation from CLI*

5. VM Migration

We tested the migration/live migration of an instance targeting a particular hypervisor. Migration in OpenStack refers to moving a virtual machine (VM) from one compute node to another. This process can be either a **cold migration** (see Figure 8, Figure 9 and Figure 10) or a **live migration** (see Figure 12). In a cold migration, the VM is powered off during the move, meaning that any services or applications running on the instance will experience downtime. The state of the VM is saved, transferred to the new node, and then restored after the migration is complete.

Live migration, on the other hand, allows a running VM to be moved to another compute node without disrupting the services or applications running on it. The instance remains operational during the process, with only a brief pause that is usually imperceptible to users. This makes live migration ideal for maintenance or load-balancing tasks, as it minimizes service interruptions. The key difference between the two lies in downtime: cold migration involves powering off the instance, while live migration keeps it running throughout the process.

Migration test

```

root@infra12-utility-container-892ee8b1:~# openstack server list
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| ID | Name | Status | Networks | Image | Flavor |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| d66de7b3-640a-49cf-b229-99732a1abb50 | vm_test_mig_2 | ACTIVE | biomics=193.205.32.234 | Ubuntu2205 | Test_Flavor |
| f7a7f65b-88c5-42f4-863e-694d388d79b8 | vm_test_migration | ACTIVE | biomics=193.205.32.221 | N/A (booted from volume) | Test_Flavor |
| d20d30fd-d739-44f5-9c87-7a311dd51119 | vm_disk_speed_test | ACTIVE | biomics=193.205.32.238 | N/A (booted from volume) | Test_Flavor |
| da08344b-b072-43a9-b8de-7d9314f0c0cf | vm_test_gianlu | SHUTOFF | biomics-private-vlan=192.168.245.151 | N/A (booted from volume) | Test_Flavor |
| 6c73efee-25d1-4776-bb8d-0dfb778e17e4 | vm_gpu | SHUTOFF | biomics=193.205.32.228 | N/A (booted from volume) | gpu_flavor2 |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
root@infra12-utility-container-892ee8b1:~# openstack server migrate --os-compute-api-version 2.56 --host computebm37 d66de7b3-640a-49cf-b229-99732a1abb50
root@infra12-utility-container-892ee8b1:~# openstack server show d66de7b3-640a-49cf-b229-99732a1abb50 | grep hypervisor
OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:hypervisor_hostname | computebm37

```

Figure 8: *OpenStack server migration from CLI*

After running migrate command a manual confirmation is asked from the Dashboard

Figure 9: *Horizon instance overview - server migration task confirmation*

Figure 10: *Horizon instance overview - server migration task ongoing*

Live Migration test

In this test we live-migrated the instance from the hypervisor (host) computebm119 (Figure 11) to computebm43 (Figure 12)

```
root@infra12-utility-container-892ee8b1:~# openstack server show 13998e7e-d3bb-44d6-8bf1-08564d2393be -f json | more
{
  "OS-DCF:diskConfig": "MANUAL",
  "OS-EXT-AZ:availability_zone": "nova",
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:host": "computebm119.cnrbiomics.local",
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:hostname": "vm-test-mig-4",
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:hypervisor_hostname": "computebm119.cnrbiomics.local",
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:instance_name": "instance-000000e5",
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:kernel_id": "",
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:launch_index": 0,
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:ramdisk_id": "",
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:reservation_id": "r-gxu0h32a",
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:root_device_name": "/dev/vda",
```

Figure 11: *OpenStack server host check from CLI*

```
root@infra12-utility-container-892ee8b1:~# openstack --os-compute-api-version 2.30 server migrate --live --host computebm43.cnrbiomics.local 13998e7e-d3bb-44d6-8bf1-08564d2393be
root@infra12-utility-container-892ee8b1:~# openstack server show 13998e7e-d3bb-44d6-8bf1-08564d2393be -f json | more
{
  "OS-DCF:diskConfig": "MANUAL",
  "OS-EXT-AZ:availability_zone": "nova",
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:host": "computebm43.cnrbiomics.local",
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:hostname": "vm-test-mig-4",
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:hypervisor_hostname": "computebm43.cnrbiomics.local",
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:instance_name": "instance-000000e5",
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:kernel_id": "",
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:launch_index": 0,
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:ramdisk_id": "",
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:reservation_id": "r-gxu0h32a",
  "OS-EXT-SRV-ATTR:root_device_name": "/dev/vda",
```

Figure 12: *OpenStack server live migration and host check from CLI*

6. Disk Speed Performance (HDD vs SSD external volumes)

In order to check whether the SSDs are correctly seen by OpenStack's VMs, a test to measure the write speed of a 10 GB file on an HDD volume (see Tab.14) and on an SSD volume (see Tab.15) has been performed.

By iterating the measurements 10 times, the results shown in the following tables were obtained:

HDD		
Test number	Speed (MB/s)	Time (s)
1	58.00	185.18
2	58.90	182.43
3	58.70	183.09
4	58.30	181.24
5	58.60	183.23
6	61.90	173.45
7	62.90	170.80
8	65.20	164.66
9	62.60	171.45
10	63.10	170.20
	AVERAGE SPEED (MB/s)	AVERAGE TIME (s)
	60.82	176.58
	SPEED STD DEV (MB/s)	TIME STD DEV (s)
	2.59	7.21

Tab.14: *Disk speed and elapsed writing time for HDDs*

SSD		
Test number	Speed (MB/s)	Time (s)
1	223.00	48.28
2	224.00	48.03
3	225.00	47.87
4	220.00	48.76
5	222.00	48.48
6	220.00	48.84
7	219.00	49.15
8	224.00	48.09
9	221.00	48.58
10	223.00	48.27
	AVERAGE SPEED (MB/s)	AVERAGE TIME (s)
	222.10	48.43
	SPEED STD DEV (MB/s)	TIME STD DEV (s)
	2.02	0.40

Tab.15: *Disk speed and elapsed writing time for SSDs*

We observe that using SSD disks the average speed (MB/s) is almost four times greater than using HDDs while getting an elapsed writing time reduction of about 73% .

Benchmark study: Cloud solutions for the random shotgun metagenomic analysis

Introduction

The aim of the benchmark study is to evaluate the performance and robustness of the CNR-ITB Cloud infrastructure by simulating the kind of workloads it was specifically designed to handle. This is done by stress-testing the system using a typical metagenomic analysis, such as a random shotgun sequencing pipeline [6], which is a common and computationally demanding task in biomedical research. By running this benchmark, the study aims to assess how well the Cloud infrastructure can manage intensive data analysis, handle large datasets and ensure high availability and scalability for research purposes. This test is essential to validate that the Cloud is capable of supporting real-world scientific workflows while maintaining efficient performance, resource allocation and reliable operation under heavy load conditions.

The purpose of this benchmark study is to evaluate the performance, scalability, and robustness of the CNR-ITB Cloud infrastructure by simulating real-world workloads that it was specifically designed to support. This assessment is conducted by stress-testing the system using a typical random shotgun metagenomic pipeline, a widely used and computationally intensive method in biomedical research.

Shotgun metagenomics involves the high-throughput sequencing of environmental or clinical samples to analyze microbial communities at the genomic level. This approach generates massive datasets, requiring substantial computational resources for data preprocessing, assembly, alignment, taxonomic classification, functional annotation and downstream analysis. The pipeline places high demands on CPU performance, memory management, storage throughput and network bandwidth, making it an ideal workload for testing the capabilities of a cloud-based infrastructure.

Through this benchmark study, we aim to assess the following key aspects of the CNR-ITB Cloud:

1. **Computational Performance** – How efficiently the cloud infrastructure handles different stages of the metagenomic pipeline, including raw sequence processing, genome assembly, and annotation.
2. **Scalability** – The ability of the Cloud environment to dynamically allocate resources as workload intensity varies, ensuring smooth execution for both small-scale and large-scale studies.
3. **Storage and Data Management** – The Cloud's efficiency in handling large datasets, including read/write speeds, IOPS performance and data transfer capabilities.

4. **Parallel Processing and Resource Utilization** – Evaluating the Cloud’s capacity to distribute tasks across multiple nodes efficiently, maximizing parallelism while preventing resource bottlenecks.

5. **High Availability and Fault Tolerance** – Ensuring the infrastructure remains stable and operational under high-load conditions, including the resilience of virtual machines, storage systems and job schedulers.

6. **Cost-effectiveness** – Assessing the balance between performance and resource consumption to ensure sustainable usage for large-scale research projects.

By conducting this benchmark study, we validate whether the CNR-ITB Cloud meets the computational and data management needs of a typical biological study while maintaining reliability, efficiency, and scalability. The insights gained will also help to optimize resource provisioning, fine-tune system configurations and guide for future improvements in the Cloud infrastructure to better support cutting-edge biomedical research.

Benchmark Study

Random shotgun metagenomic samples can be analyzed in various ways, but one of the more resource-intensive protocols involves the extraction of Metagenome-Assembled Genomes (MAGs). This presents an opportunity to define requirements for virtual machines (VMs) that will support the analysis of such samples. To this end, we selected a study (PRJNA1226738), from the SRA database, that includes metagenomic samples of human fecal matter, with a total of 26 samples and an average of 22 GBytes of sequence reads per sample. The VM specifications were 32 cores, 128 GBytes of RAM and 2 TBytes of disk space.

The protocol used required the SRA Toolkit [7], where the `prefetch` command was used to download the project files, and the `fastq-dump` command was used to extract FASTQ files for further analysis. While the SRA Toolkit was downloaded directly from its source repository, the other tools were installed using `micromamba` from the Conda package management system (www.anaconda.org). The analysis began by assembling the reads of each sample using Megahit [8] with default parameters. Each sample required about 50-70 minutes using all available cores.

The next step involved filtering the assembly to include only contigs with a length greater than or equal to 1 kbp, followed by using Bowtie2 [9] to align the reads of each sample back to its corresponding assembly. This step took about 40-100 minutes on average, again using all available cores. It was necessary for the subsequent step in the protocol, which involved using a binning tool to extract MAGs from each sample. The chosen binner, Metabat2 [10], completed its task on these types of samples in a matter of minutes.

One of the objectives of this test was to understand the VM characteristics required for metagenomic studies. We used a project from a relatively simple community with a per-sample protocol. Given the time needed to complete it and the resources used, we anticipate that the

same specifications can be applied to more complex communities, such as rumen gut microbiota, with up to a 2x increase in sequencing depth. While this test does not comprise a full pipeline, the most computationally intensive steps were evaluated, and the downstream analysis will depend on the specific study.

Conclusions

In this report, we have detailed the design, implementation and deployment of a high-availability OpenStack Cloud infrastructure at CNR-ITB, leveraging Ceph as the storage backend and Ansible for installation, orchestration and automation. The solution presented addresses the growing demands for a scalable, resilient and flexible Cloud platform that meets the critical performance and availability requirements of research environments.

By integrating Ceph with OpenStack, we achieved a unified, distributed storage system capable of handling object, block and file storage with high reliability. The use of Ansible for configuration management and automation ensured consistent deployments, reducing the complexity of managing multiple components across various nodes.

The implementation of high availability at both the control plane and storage layers was crucial in eliminating single points of failure, significantly improving uptime and minimizing disruptions. With the addition of failover mechanisms, redundant networking, and clustered services, the platform is now equipped to handle unexpected failures with minimal impact on ongoing operations.

This project demonstrates the effectiveness of open-source technologies, such as OpenStack and Ceph, in delivering robust Cloud infrastructure solutions. The successful deployment at CNR-ITB sets a foundation for future scalability and can serve as a model for other organizations seeking to implement similar high-availability cloud environments.

As the needs of the scientific community continue to evolve, this infrastructure can be further expanded and optimized to accommodate larger workloads and more complex applications, ensuring CNR-ITB remains at the forefront of research computing.

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The computing infrastructure is hosted at the CNR laboratory within the ReCaS data center in Bari and includes high-performance servers, GPU-equipped machines for ML/DL/AI acceleration, and fast SSD-based storage. In addition, a large-scale parallel storage system (5 PB) ensures long-term data preservation.

This ICT facility is part of the services provided by the Compute Platform of ELIXIR-IT [11] (ELIXIR-IIB, Italian Infrastructure for Bioinformatics), the Italian node of ELIXIR [12], the ESFRI European infrastructure for biological data [13]. Its primary objective is to support research in the life sciences and their translational applications in medicine, the environment, biotechnology, and society.

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